

SUSTAINABLE FOOD PACKAGING: EMPOWERING CONSUMERS WITH COLOR-CODED SUGAR CONTENT AWARENESS

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Abstract: *The purpose of developing the color-coding system development serves a dual purpose: enhancing awareness of sugar content in foods and to promote sustainability. Our study focused on dairy products on the Slovenian market and addressed hidden sugars and associated health risks. By integrating sustainability, we aimed to raise awareness of sugar content through packaging design with a consistent labeling and coding approach. Our research included key questions to ensure labeling effectiveness and sustainability. We focused on creating an impartial labeling system, organizing the hierarchy and layout of food information, and integrating seamlessly with existing packaging. Critical to successful implementation was evaluating the impact of the information design on consumer behavior in the area of food packaging. Based on our discoveries, we developed several variants of a multicolor and one colour labeling system. These variants differed in key information graphics, color palettes, placement, and formats. To illustrate the application of the system, we designed packaging for a fictitious brand and implemented the code system accordingly. The final step was to embed the packaging design into 3D models for each food category. Consistent and coherent color-coded labels were integrated into the packaging, effectively attracting consumer attention while providing important information. With sustainability at the forefront, our design approach aims to promote environmentally friendly practices from production to disposal. This holistic strategy promotes environmental responsibility throughout the packaging process.*

Keywords: Sustainable food packaging; color coding system; sugar content awareness; consumer empowerment; packaging design

1 INTRODUCTION

Sugar consumption is ubiquitous in the modern diets and is present in almost all processed foods. It is important to distinguish between natural and added sugars, as they have different effects on health. Added sugar, while offering benefits, can lead to overconsumption and health problems. Therefore, it is important to closely examine the ingredients of products. While excessive sugar is known to be present in products such as sugary drinks and confectionery, even supposedly healthy options such as yogurt, milk, and cereal can contain hidden sugar, making it difficult for consumers to be aware (College of California, 2023). Efforts to clarify sugar content on labels have resulted in different formats worldwide. Research by Scapin et al. (2021) found that interpretive formats that combine sugar content in grams with colors, indicators such as "high sugar content," or percentage of daily value are most effective. Labeling strategies using textual warnings, health claims, and graphic representations with teaspoons were moderately effective. Erickson and Slavin (2015) examined consumer behavior in response to the new sugar guidelines, while Coyle et al. (2020) found that interpretive formats that conveyed information about sugar, particularly those that indicated high sugar content, improved consumer understanding and led to healthier food choices.

Uniform labeling systems, such as Slovenia's, are still poorly researched and absent from the marketplace. Challenges remain in the European Union due to inconsistent nutritional data and lack of knowledge about dietary habits (Eržen, 2014). Differing terminology for sugars-"added" versus "free"-contributes to confusion, which is exacerbated by incomplete sugar content labeling. Analysis of sugar content poses problems because different chemical methods, such as quantitative and chromatographic methods, are both unable to distinguish natural from added sugar (Goldfein et al., 2015). Consumer understanding is complicated by complex terminology. The ubiquity of sugar warrants nuanced differentiation on labels. Effective formats with color-coded indicators or percent daily value information facilitate understanding and healthier food choices. It remains difficult to create consistent labeling systems due to inconsistencies in terminology, measurement methods and consumer understanding. The study sought to enhance awareness regarding sugar content in dairy products and cereals using packaging design and to develop a consistent labeling system applicable to various products.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research adopted a systematic methodology comprising five sequential stages to assess sugar content in dairy products and subsequently integrate findings into 3D packaging arrangements. Furthermore, an innovative multi- and one color-coded labeling scheme were devised to enhance visual representation.

2.1 Methods and sampling

The research encompassed five distinct steps:

1. Sugar content analysis covered a wide range of dairy products in the Slovenian market, classified based on the results.
2. Detailed graphic analysis and packaging hierarchy design for specific food groups (e.g., yogurt, milk, butter) were undertaken, considering variations like plastic cups, bottles, cartons, and boxes.
3. A comprehensive graphical analysis and global comparison of diverse labeling methods (symbols, colors, formats) in Slovenia and other countries led to the creation of multiple labeling versions with distinct symbols, colors, formats, and layouts.
4. Developed labeling systems were applied to conceptual packaging (labels) for an imaginary brand, aligning with the prior analysis.
5. Facilitating realistic representation, 3D packaging models were generated for each food group (yogurt, milk, butter), each showcasing two labeling variations and colours using program Blender (NeoGeo, USA).

2.2 Analysis of sugar content in dairy products

The study included an extensive evaluation of dairy items present in the Slovenian market, encompassing a total of 47 samples from 12 distinct producers. The samples were thoughtfully chosen to ensure representation across diverse product categories. Across four food groups, multiple products were analyzed across various stores as outlined below:

- Yoghurt or milk bottles/bottles: 10 samples
- Butter packets: 12 samples
- Milk cartons: 10 samples
- Yoghurt containers: 15 samples

3 RESULTS

3.1 Results of analysis of present sugar content in dairy products

Using samples that included natural, fruit, and protein yogurts, statistical frequency distribution methods were used to form classes by ascending sugar content in the products. These classes facilitated the subsequent development of a coherent color-coded scale that allowed different colors to be assigned to specific classes. For example, the blue color was assigned to the class with the lowest sugar content. Within the product spectrum, sugar content ranged from a minimum of 3.8 g to a maximum of 14.0 g. The levels or classes of sugar in food were created based on analyses of dairy and cereal products available on the Slovenian market. The sugar scale contains five classes ranging from the lowest to the highest sugar content (Table 1). In contrast to the middle three open intervals, the minimum and maximum classes have less than 3 g of sugar and more than 15.4 g of sugar, respectively.

Table 1. Ascending classes of amounts of sugar in grams.

Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high
< 0.3	– 7.9	8.0 – 10.4	10.5 – 12.9	> 15.4

3.2 Preparation and design of a coding system with colors and typography

The creation of a multi-hued scale was driven by the objective of swiftly and effortlessly recognizing sugar content in products. This color-coded approach facilitates a more lucid and succinct assessment of sugar levels, expediting the acquisition of desired information for customers. Classes have been associated with specific color codes, fostering an intuitive and rational link between sugar quantity and its corresponding color (Figure 1a and 1b). The scale presented in Figure 1a boasts a sleek, elongated rectangular design. Within this framework, the classes are segmented into smaller sections, demarcated by white stripes seamlessly blending into the backdrop. Each class features distinct primary and secondary information, separated by negative space that forms an arrow pointing towards the relevant data. The shapes' corners exhibit a subtle roundness, contributing to a welcoming yet uncluttered visual presentation. One solution would be for the colors on the scale to differ significantly in brightness, but this could prove inconsistent, unclear, or lacking in contrast with five different consecutive classes. Therefore, we also created black and white symbols to indicate the primary data and placed them on a scale (Figure 1c).

Besides the monochrome scale with symbols, we have also created the possibility of a monochrome scale that is not so illustrated, namely with simple patterns to mark the class (Figure 1d).

Figure 1. Variations of labelling for sugar content in dairy products: a) multi-coloured scale with words and sugar content, b) multi-coloured scale with lettering and sugar content, c) black-white coloured scale with figures and sugar content, d) monochrome scale

3. 3 Code placement on different dairy packaging products

Equally significant was the consideration of feasible scale placement on the packaging—ensuring logical positioning for swift recognition, while maintaining a non-disruptive coexistence with other food-related details. Presented in Figure 2 there are diverse scale placements on a product sample package for yogurt, milk and butter. Due to one and multi-colour labelling, both variations are presented. With this innovative approach not only promotes eco-friendly practices but also equips consumers with the tools to make informed dietary choices. By intertwining sustainability and sugar awareness, this initiative fosters a more health-conscious and environmentally responsible future.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 2. Variations of multi colour and black-white code labelling for sugar content in dairy products: a) yogurt, b) butter and c) milk.

For easier presentation of the designed packaging and scales, we created 3D models of the packaging for each food group using the Blender software tool. We designed a model for a bottle with a label, a butter with a lid, a milk or yogurt carton. We designed the models using simpler modeling techniques. We made sure to model at a realistic scale so that the sizes of the packages were in proportion (Figure 3). Placements for black-white coding combinations could be on the same place as multi-coloured variation.

Figure 3. 3D presentations of dairy products and colour labelling of sugar content on a) yogurt, b) milk and c) butter.

3 CONCLUSIONS

When evaluating the existing methods of nutrition labeling, it becomes clear that the Slovenian market lacks a uniform system for labeling sugar content. Consequently, our approach involved devising and contrasting diverse design solutions that vary in terms of format, colors, and interpretability (graphical visualizations). This led us to create different types of scales, differing in how they present primary information. We crafted a multi-color scale with word or letter

representation, alongside a single-color scale incorporating symbols or patterns in place of primary information.

Thoughtful contemplation was given to optimizing the scale placement on packaging, ensuring that sugar content information captures customers' attention without conflicting with the established visual identity. Drawing inspiration from our meticulous sample analysis, the visual aesthetics of our packaging evoke a sophisticated, natural, and subtly playful impression.

In our label design process, we also strategically considered the potential for adaptability, ensuring these labels can seamlessly find application across a diverse range of future food packaging scenarios.

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